

ANALYSIS OF GIRLS' PHYSICAL FITNESS INDICATORS

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Abstract: In order to increase the general physical fitness of female students, an experimental field was organized in the sports hall of Fergana State University.

Keywords: Physical training, functional capabilities, physical qualities of strength, speed, endurance, agility and flexibility.

Physical training of female students is considered as one of the most important components of sports training, and it is understood as a process aimed at all-round development of the organism, education of physical qualities of strengthening health, and creation of a solid functional base for all other types of sports training. It is considered a foundation, a necessary basis for achieving high results in the general physical fitness of female students.

It is aimed at solving the following tasks:

1. Increasing the functional capabilities of the body of female students;
2. Development of physical qualities of strength, quickness, endurance, agility and flexibility;
3. Eliminating deficiencies in the physical development of female students.

In order to increase the general physical fitness of female students, an experimental field was organized in the sports hall of Fergana State University.

When applying loads in a complex direction aimed at the development of various physical qualities, we first took into account the following:

1. Reasonable consistency, that is, the order and sequence of introducing loads into the training that help to develop various qualities, was determined;
2. A reasonable ratio of the volume and intensity of loads was chosen.

The training of physical qualities consists of training the ability to master complex movements in terms of balance measurement, and secondly, training the ability to review movement activities in accordance with the requirements that need to be mastered suddenly.

Thus, if we compare our scientific research work, the experimental group had 17.7 seconds in running 100 meters at the beginning, and it improved to 16.7 seconds at the end of the experiment. The female students in the control group had an initial time of 18.0 seconds, and by the end of the study improved to 17.4 seconds.

Figure 1. Dynamics of the initial and final performance of female students in the 100-meter run

The main way to develop and train speed means the formation of a new variety of movement skills. In order to develop speed, it is possible to develop speed by jumping backwards, forwards, sideways, running around, using various tactical combinations in games, changing partners frequently during exercises, and freely learning and applying folk movement games.

It was found that the use of folk movement games in the education of agility from female students in the experimental group was statistically significantly higher ($t=3.8$ $P < 0.001$) than the result of the female students in the control group.